

Maximino S. Laurete Sr. Central School Grade 6 Academic Performance Before, During, and After the COVID-19 Pandemic

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic caused unprecedented disruptions in Philippine basic education, shifting instruction from face-to-face to modular learning. This study examined how these changes affected the academic performance of Grade 6 learners at Maximino S. Laurete Sr. Central School (MSLCS) across three phases: pre-pandemic, pandemic, and post-pandemic recovery. A descriptive quantitative design anchored on the Input-Process-Output (IPO) framework was employed. Final grades from 42 Grade 6 learners were traced from Grade 1 (pre-pandemic), Grades 2-3 (pandemic), and Grades 4-5 (post-pandemic). The Kruskal-Wallis H-test was used to compare performance across clusters (Satisfactory, Very Satisfactory, Outstanding). Significant variation was observed in the Satisfactory cluster ($H = 12.85$, $df = 5$, $p = 0.025$). Median grades declined during the pandemic (Year 2 = 83) but improved post-pandemic (Year 4 = 88). In contrast, the Very Satisfactory cluster ($H = 8.46$, $p = 0.132$) and Outstanding cluster ($H = 9.08$, $p = 0.106$) showed no statistically significant differences, with mean grades ranging narrowly from 85.21-87.57 and 87.33-92.67, respectively. Findings suggest that lower-performing learners were more vulnerable to modality shifts, while higher achievers maintained stability. Policy implications point to the need for equity-focused remediation, adaptive teaching strategies, and contingency planning. However, reliance on grade data alone limits the analysis, underscoring the importance of mixed-method approaches in future studies.

Keywords: COVID-19 pandemic, academic performance, Grade 6, instructional transition, learning recovery, Philippines

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1. Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic prompted a monumental shift in education worldwide, forcing a rapid transition from traditional in-person classes to remote and modular learning modalities (Bertoletti & Karpiński, 2024). In the Philippines, this transition exacerbated long-standing challenges such as limited infrastructure and unequal access to quality education (Lu, 2024). The World Bank (2022) reported that learning poverty in the country surged from 69.5% in 2019 to 91% in 2021, indicating that nine out of ten Filipino children under the age of 10 could not read a simple text (Lu, 2024). In response, the government introduced recovery programs, including the Academic Recovery and Accessible Learning (ARAL) Program, to mitigate learning loss and restore educational outcomes (Academic Recovery and Accessible Learning Program Act, 2024).

Global studies have highlighted multiple dimensions of the crisis. The digital divide limited students' access to online platforms, especially in disadvantaged households (Kuhfeld & Tarasawa, 2020), while the sudden transition disrupted routines and heightened students' stress, loneliness, and disengagement (Meinck et al., 2022; Tadesse & Muluye, 2020). For many education systems, the challenge extended beyond sustaining instruction to ensuring equity and mental health support.

As schools reopened, attention shifted toward addressing "learning gaps" caused by prolonged disruptions (Allen et al., 2024; Cortés-Albornoz et al., 2023). Evidence suggests that younger and socioeconomically disadvantaged learners were most affected, particularly in literacy and numeracy (Engzell et al., 2021; Kuhfeld et al., 2022). In the Philippine context, modular distance learning was the primary instructional mode during lockdowns. While it allowed continuity, it faced issues of uneven distribution, content quality, and weak monitoring of learner progress (Cajurao et al., 2023; Talimodao & Madrigal, 2021). The Department of Education acknowledged significant learning losses and called for targeted interventions (Hernando-Malipot, 2022).

While the pandemic's overall impact on student learning outcomes has been widely documented, few studies have traced performance trends across distinct stages of the crisis—before, during, and after school closures—at the elementary level in the Philippines. This gap is especially relevant for Grade 6 students, who experienced disruptions during critical years leading to their transition to secondary education.

The present study addresses this gap by examining the academic performance of Grade 6 students at Maximino S. Laurete Sr. Central School (MSLCS) across three phases: pre-pandemic, during pandemic, and post-pandemic recovery. Using the Input-Process-Output (IPO) framework and non-parametric statistical analysis, the study analyzes variations in performance clusters to provide evidence on how learners were affected and how recovery unfolded. By doing so, it contributes to local and international discussions on resilience, learning recovery, and strategies for building inclusive and adaptive education systems in times of crisis.

2. Methodology

2.1. Research Design

This study employed a descriptive quantitative research design to examine the trends in the academic performance of Grade 6 learners at Maximino S. Laurete Sr. Central School (MSLCS) across three key periods: before the COVID-19 pandemic, during its height, and in the post-pandemic transition phase. This design was selected to systematically document patterns in final grades and analyze differences using non-parametric statistical methods.

2.2. Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of this study is anchored in the Input-Process-Output (IPO) model, which is a widely recognized approach in instructional design for illustrating how contextual factors, resources, and activities interact to produce intended outcomes (Richey, et al., 2010). In this study, the IPO framework organizes the flow from the students' academic records and learning modalities (Input), through systematic data gathering and statistical analysis (Process), to the identification of performance trends and implications for educational practice (Output). See Figure 1 for further reference.

Figure 1. *Input-Process-Output (IPO) Conceptual Framework of the Study*

The input includes learners' final grades in core subjects, collected from Grade 1 (pre-pandemic baseline), Grades 2-3 (pandemic phase), and Grades 4-5 (post-pandemic recovery). It also considers school-level interventions such as the use of printed modular learning and subsequent remedial programs. While the process involves data collection through permanent student records, ensuring proper authorization and confidentiality. The collected grades were then analyzed using the Kruskal-Wallis H-Test, a non-parametric equivalent of one-way ANOVA, to determine whether statistically significant differences exist across the three periods. Finally, the output consists of observed trends in academic performance, interpretation of the findings in light of relevant literature, and implications for improving learning continuity and resilience during future crises.

2.3. Locale and Participants

The study was conducted at Maximino S. Laurete Sr. Central School, a public elementary school in the Philippines. The target participants were the Grade 6 students

enrolled during School Year 2024–2025. Academic records were drawn from the students' School Form 10, covering final grades from Grade 1 to Grade 5.

2.4. Data Collection Procedure

Before any data were collected, the researchers formally sought and obtained written approval from the school principal, the registrar, and the Grade 6 teacher-adviser. This permission allowed access to the relevant academic records needed for the study. Throughout the process, strict confidentiality measures were observed: all student information was anonymized, and the data were securely handled to ensure that no learner names or identifying details were disclosed.

The academic records collected for analysis were organized into three distinct periods reflecting the key phases of the pandemic's impact on schooling. The pre-pandemic phase included the students' final grades from Grade 1, representing their baseline performance during regular face-to-face instruction. The pandemic phase covered the abrupt shift to modular learning, with the students' final grades from Grades 2 and 3 combined to calculate an average for this period. Finally, the post-pandemic phase reflected the return to in-person classes and included the average of the students' final grades from Grades 4 and 5, when schools focused on resuming normal operations and addressing learning gaps through catch-up interventions.

2.5. Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics (means, medians, mean ranks) were computed to identify general trends in performance across the three periods. The Kruskal-Wallis H-Test was employed to test for significant differences among the grade clusters. If the test indicated significance, post hoc pairwise comparisons were recommended to pinpoint specific periods with meaningful differences.

2.6. Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to ethical standards for educational research. All records were anonymized, used solely for academic purposes, and presented in aggregate form to protect the identities of students. Permission letters and approval documents were filed with the school's administration prior to data collection.

2.7. Limitations of Scope

Because this study focused on a single public elementary school and one Grade 6 cohort, the findings should be interpreted with caution. They illustrate performance patterns within this specific school context but cannot be generalized to all Grade 6 learners in the Philippines. Nonetheless, the results provide valuable case-based evidence that contributes to the broader understanding of pandemic-related learning trends in Philippine basic education.

3. Results

This study analyzed the trends in academic performance of Grade 6 learners at Maximino S. Laurete Sr. Central School (MSLCS) across three phases: pre-pandemic, during the pandemic, and post-pandemic. The findings are organized by performance clusters – Satisfactory, Very Satisfactory, and Outstanding – following the school’s grading scheme.

3.1. Academic Performance Trends

This presents the trends in academic performance across three performance clusters—Satisfactory, Very Satisfactory, and Outstanding—examined over the pre-pandemic, pandemic, and post-pandemic phases. By applying the Kruskal-Wallis H-test, the analysis investigates whether median grades varied significantly across grade levels and phases of learning delivery. The descriptive statistics highlight how learners’ grades shifted during the transition from traditional classroom instruction to modular learning and later to the resumption of face-to-face classes. The results provide insight into how different groups of students were affected by these shifts, with some clusters showing significant variation across phases while others demonstrated consistent levels of achievement despite disruptions in the learning environment.

3.1.1. Satisfactory Performance Cluster

The performance trends for the Satisfactory cluster are illustrated in Figure 2, which presents the mean ranks and median grades across the pre-pandemic, pandemic, and post-pandemic phases.

Figure 2. Mean Ranks and Median Grades for the Satisfactory Cluster Across Grade Levels

Kruskal-Wallis Test: Grade versus Year				
Descriptive Statistics				
Year	N	Median	Mean Rank	Z-Value
1	7	84	16.1	-1.28
2	7	83	11.1	-2.46
3	7	85	20.5	-0.24
4	7	88	31.9	2.45
5	7	87	26.4	1.15
6	7	84	23.1	0.39
Overall	42		21.5	
Test				
Null hypothesis	H ₀ : All medians are equal			
Alternative hypothesis	H ₁ : At least one median is different			
Method	DF	H-Value	P-Value	
Not adjusted for ties	5	12.69	0.026	
Adjusted for ties	5	12.85	0.025	

The Kruskal-Wallis test revealed significant differences in grades within the satisfactory cluster across grade levels ($H = 12.85$, $df = 5$, $p = 0.025$). Median grades ranged

from 83 in Year 2 to 88 in Year 4, with mean ranks also lowest in Year 2 (11.1) and highest in Year 4 (31.9). These results indicate that performance in this cluster declined during the pandemic years (Years 2–3) but showed improvement in the post-pandemic recovery phase (Years 4–5) as face-to-face classes and support programs resumed.

For this cluster, the Kruskal-Wallis H-Test revealed a statistically significant difference in grades among the three phases. The computed H-value was 12.85 with an adjusted p-value of 0.025, which is below the standard 0.05 significance level. This result indicates that at least one phase’s median grade differed meaningfully from the others, reflecting how performance shifted during modular learning and the subsequent recovery.

The descriptive trend shows that learners in this cluster generally experienced lower grades during the pandemic period (Grades 2–3) but showed improvement during the post-pandemic recovery (Grades 4–5) as face-to-face learning and intervention programs resumed.

3.1.2. Very Satisfactory Performance Cluster

The performance trends for the Very Satisfactory cluster are shown in Figure 3, which displays the mean ranks and median grades across the three phases.

Figure 3. Mean Ranks and Median Grades for the Very Satisfactory Cluster Across Grade Levels

Kruskal-Wallis Test: Grade versus Year				
Descriptive Statistics				
Year	N	Median	Mean Rank	Z-Value
1	14	88.0	55.3	2.15
2	14	87.0	44.0	0.26
3	14	84.0	30.8	-1.97
4	14	87.5	47.1	0.77
5	14	85.0	37.5	-0.83
6	14	86.0	40.3	-0.37
Overall	84		42.5	

Test			
Null hypothesis	H ₀ : All medians are equal		
Alternative hypothesis	H ₁ : At least one median is different		
Method	DF	H-Value	P-Value
Not adjusted for ties	5	8.33	0.139
Adjusted for ties	5	8.46	0.132

The Kruskal-Wallis test was used to compare grades in the very satisfactory cluster across six year levels. Median grades ranged from 84.0 in Year 3 to 88.0 in Year 1, with mean ranks also lowest in Year 3 (30.8) and highest in Year 1 (55.3). Although descriptive results suggest stronger performance in Year 1 and relatively weaker outcomes in Year 3, the test

showed no statistically significant differences among groups ($H = 8.46$, $df = 5$, $p = 0.132$). This indicates that grade distributions within the very satisfactory cluster remained generally consistent across grade levels.

For this cluster, the Kruskal-Wallis test found no statistically significant difference in grades among the phases. The adjusted p-value was greater than 0.05, indicating that any small variations in median grades are likely due to random differences rather than systematic effects of the changing learning delivery.

This result suggests that many students in this group maintained consistent performance even during the transition to modular learning and the return to in-person classes.

3.1.3. Outstanding Performance Cluster

The performance trends for the Outstanding cluster are presented in Figure 4, which depicts the mean ranks and median grades for this group across the three phases.

Figure 4. Mean Ranks and Median Grades for the Outstanding Cluster Across Grade Levels

Kruskal-Wallis Test: Grade versus Year				
Descriptive Statistics				
Year	N	Median	Mean Rank	Z-Value
1	6	91.5	23.3	1.23
2	6	90.5	19.5	0.25
3	6	86.0	9.4	-2.31
4	6	90.5	13.6	-1.25
5	6	92.0	22.1	0.91
6	6	94.0	23.1	1.17
Overall	36		18.5	

Test				
Null hypothesis	H_0 : All medians are equal			
Alternative hypothesis	H_1 : At least one median is different			
Method	DF	H-Value	P-Value	
Not adjusted for ties	5	8.91	0.113	
Adjusted for ties	5	9.08	0.106	

The Kruskal-Wallis test was conducted to examine grade differences in the outstanding cluster across six year levels. Median grades ranged from 86.0 in Year 3 to 94.0 in Year 6, with mean ranks also lowest in Year 3 (9.4) and highest in Years 1 and 6 (23.3 and 23.1, respectively). Although the descriptive results point to weaker performance in Year 3 and stronger outcomes in Years 5 and 6, the test revealed no statistically significant differences ($H = 9.08$, $df = 5$, $p = 0.106$). These findings suggest that grade distributions in the outstanding cluster were largely consistent across grade levels.

The test showed no statistically significant difference for this cluster, with an adjusted p-value above 0.05. Although slight fluctuations were observed – with a minor dip during the pandemic – these changes were not statistically meaningful.

This finding indicates that students in the Outstanding cluster were largely able to sustain high levels of performance regardless of the changes in learning modalities.

3.2. Summary of Descriptive Statistics

To better visualize how grades were distributed within each performance cluster across the three phases, separate histograms are provided for the Satisfactory, Very Satisfactory, and Outstanding clusters.

For the Satisfactory cluster, Figure 5 shows a histogram of the number of learners falling within this band during the pre-pandemic, pandemic, and post-pandemic periods. This visual highlights the increase in students categorized as Satisfactory during the pandemic and the decline as performance recovered afterward.

Figure 5. Histogram of Final Grade Distribution for the Satisfactory Cluster Across Grade Levels

The histogram on Figure 5 shows that grade distributions within the satisfactory cluster shifted across year levels. Lower means and wider spreads were observed in Years 2 and 3, reflecting weaker performance during the pandemic phase of modular learning. In contrast, Years 4 and 5 displayed higher means and more concentrated distributions, indicating recovery as face-to-face instruction resumed. Years 1 and 6 clustered closer to the overall average, suggesting stable but moderate performance. Overall, the distribution pattern highlights the impact of the pandemic on learner outcomes and the subsequent improvement during the post-pandemic recovery phase.

For the Very Satisfactory cluster, Figure 6 presents the histogram depicting the relative stability in the number of learners achieving this level of performance across the three phases.

Figure 6. Histogram of Final Grade Distribution for the Very Satisfactory Cluster Across Three Phases

The histogram on Figure 6 shows that grade distributions in the very satisfactory cluster were closely clustered across all years. Mean grades ranged narrowly from 85.21 in Year 3 to 87.57 in Year 1, with similar levels of variability. These results indicate that students in this cluster maintained consistent performance across the pre-pandemic, pandemic, and post-pandemic phases, reflecting their relative stability despite shifts in learning modalities.

For the Outstanding cluster, Figure 7 displays the histogram highlighting the distribution of top-performing students in each phase. This figure shows that the number of learners in this highest cluster remained steady overall, despite minor fluctuations during the modular learning period.

The histogram on Figure 7 shows that the outstanding cluster consistently performed at the highest level, with mean grades ranging from 87.33 in Year 3 to 92.67 in Year 1. Although some variability was observed, grade distributions remained concentrated in the upper 80s to 90s. This indicates that students in this cluster sustained exceptional performance across all phases, demonstrating resilience and adaptability regardless of changes in learning modalities.

Figure 7. Histogram of Final Grade Distribution for the Outstanding Cluster Across Three Phases

Together, these cluster-specific histograms complement the earlier statistical results by showing how the learner counts in each band shifted during and after the pandemic. The histograms provide a clear visual summary of how performance levels shifted across the three phases. The three histograms (Figures 5, 6 & 7) show a clear progression of learner performance across the Satisfactory, Very Satisfactory, and Outstanding clusters. The Satisfactory group clustered around the low to mid-80s, with moderate variability reflecting modest but consistent outcomes. The Very Satisfactory cluster showed higher concentration in the mid-80s to high 80s, indicating more stable performance across phases. Meanwhile, the Outstanding cluster displayed the highest achievement, with means in the upper 80s to low 90s and generally sustained excellence despite some variability. Overall, the distributions highlight increasing consistency and achievement as learners move from satisfactory to outstanding levels, suggesting stable academic standing across clusters over time.

4. Discussion, Recommendations, and Conclusion

The results of this study provide insights into how the COVID-19 pandemic influenced the academic performance of Grade 6 learners at Maximino S. Laurete Sr. Central School (MSLCS) across three critical phases. The significant variation observed in the Satisfactory cluster supports findings from global and local studies showing that learners at the lower and middle performance levels were particularly vulnerable to sudden shifts in learning modalities and limited support structures (Dorn et al., 2020; Kuhfeld et al., 2022). The increased number of students in this band during the pandemic period reflects the challenges of modular distance learning, particularly for households with limited resources,

unstable connectivity, or uncondusive study environments (Cajurao et al., 2023; Talimodao & Madrigal, 2021).

In contrast, the relative stability of the Very Satisfactory and Outstanding clusters aligns with previous research suggesting that higher-performing students, often equipped with self-regulation skills and stronger home support systems, were able to sustain their academic performance despite disruptions (Meinck et al., 2022; Zheng et al., 2022). Within the Input-Process-Output (IPO) framework (Richey et al., 2010), these results highlight how even limited inputs, such as printed modules and community involvement, were leveraged through school-level processes to generate outputs that reflected resilience.

From a policy perspective, these findings underscore the importance of equity-oriented interventions. While the ARAL Program and related initiatives represent a step forward in addressing pandemic learning losses, policymakers may need to refine these programs to ensure that the most vulnerable learners, those consistently clustered in the Satisfactory band, receive targeted, sustained, and context-sensitive support. National and local education policies may also prioritize integrating contingency planning into the school improvement process, establishing clear mechanisms for transitioning between modalities, and institutionalizing psychosocial support systems as part of crisis response. Strengthening teacher training on digital literacy, adaptive pedagogy, and learner well-being may also enhance preparedness for future disruptions.

At the school and community level, institutions may improve the accessibility and clarity of modular and hybrid materials, establish remediation programs for at-risk learners, and build stronger parent-school-community partnerships to sustain engagement. Monitoring and evaluation mechanisms combining quantitative performance data with qualitative learner feedback may be institutionalized to guide adjustments and ensure accountability.

It must also be noted, however, that this study relied solely on grade distributions as indicators of academic performance. While grades provide a useful snapshot of learner outcomes, they may mask variations in specific subject areas, skill competencies, or psychosocial factors that influence learning. Future research may adopt mixed methods, integrating standardized assessments, classroom observations, or learner interviews, to provide a more nuanced understanding of academic resilience and vulnerability during crises.

In conclusion, while the pandemic disrupted traditional learning, the trends among Grade 6 learners at MSLCS show that responsive interventions, adaptable teaching practices, and strong community support can mitigate setbacks. Strengthening equity-focused policies, embedding contingency planning in education systems, and addressing the limitations of grade-only analysis may enable schools and policymakers to build a more resilient and inclusive education system that safeguards both learning outcomes and learner well-being in times of crisis.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this research paper.

References

1. Adedoyin, O. B., & Soykan, E. (2020). COVID-19 pandemic and online learning: The challenges and opportunities. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 28(7), 1–13.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2020.1813180>
2. Allen, T., Whitlock, D., & Hood, J. (2024). Teaching in the Post-Pandemic Classroom. *Research Issues in Contemporary Education*, 9(3), 113–139.
<https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1463027.pdf>
3. *Academic Recovery and Accessible Learning (ARAL) Program Act, Republic Act No. 12028* (2024). https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/IRR_R.A.-12028_ARAL-ACT.pdf
4. Bertoletti, A., & Karpiński, Z. (2024). Investigating the effect of COVID-19 disruption in education using REDS data. *Large-scale Assessments in Education*, 12.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s40536-024-00195-x>
5. Cajurao, E. C., Mortel, J. C. V., Maglente, M. S. C., Dumaguin, J. R., Paloma, V. V., Rios, C. R., & Rivas, M. A. D. (2023). Modular distance learning: Perceived challenges and strategies of secondary science teachers in Mandaon District, Masbate, Philippines. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education Research*, 4(6), 2023–2037.
<https://doi.org/10.11594/ijmaber.04.06.27>
6. Cortés-Albornoz, M. C., Ramírez-Guerrero, S., García-Guáqueta, D. P., Vélez-Van-Meerbeke, A., & Talero-Gutiérrez, C. (2023). Effects of remote learning during COVID-19 lockdown on children's learning abilities and school performance: A systematic review. *International journal of educational development*, 101, 102835.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedudev.2023.102835>
7. Dorn, E., Hancock, B., Sarakatsannis, J., & Viruleg, E. (2020). COVID-19 and learning loss—Disparities grow and students need help. *McKinsey & Company*.

<https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/public-and-social-sector/our-insights/covid-19-and-learning-loss-disparities-grow-and-students-need-help>

8. Engzell, P., Frey, A., & Verhagen, M. D. (2021). Learning loss due to school closures during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 118(17), e2022376118. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2022376118>
9. Hernando-Malipot, M. (2022, August 14). DepEd reiterates commitment to address 'learning loss' during the pandemic. *Manila Bulletin*. <https://mb.com.ph/2022/8/14/depd-reiterates-commitment-to-address-learning-loss-during-the-pandemic>
10. Kuhfeld, M., Soland, J., Tarasawa, B., Johnson, A., Ruzek, E., & Liu, J. (2022). Projecting the potential impact of COVID-19 school closures on academic achievement. *Educational Researcher*, 49(8), 549–565. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X20965918>
11. Kuhfeld, M., & Tarasawa, B. (2020). The COVID-19 slide: What summer learning loss can tell us about the potential impact of school closures on student academic achievement. *The Collaborative for Student Growth Research Brief*. https://www.nwea.org/uploads/2020/04/Collaborative-Brief_Covid19-Slide-APR20.pdf
12. Lu, B. J. (2024, October 28). Literacy important for PH development. *Philippine News Agency*. <https://www.pna.gov.ph/opinion/pieces/962-literacy-important-for-ph-development>
13. Meinck, S., Fraillon, J., & Strietholt, R. (2022). *The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on education: international evidence from the Responses to Educational Disruption Survey (REDS)*. Unesco.org. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000380398>
14. Richey, R. C., Klein, J. D., & Tracey, M. W. (2010). *The Instructional Design Knowledge Base: Theory, Research, and Practice*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203840986>
15. Sing Yun, W. (2023). Digitalization challenges in education during COVID-19: A systematic review. *Cogent Education*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2023.2198981>
16. Tadesse, S., & Muluye, W. (2020). The Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic on Education System in Developing Countries: A Review. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 08(10), 159–170. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jss.2020.810011>
17. Talimodao, A. J. S., & Madrigal, D. V. (2021). Printed Modular Distance Learning in Philippine Public Elementary Schools in Time of COVID-19 Pandemic: Quality, Implementation, and Challenges. *Philippine Social Science Journal*, 4(3), 19–29. <https://doi.org/10.52006/main.v4i3.391>
18. World Bank. (2022). *The State of Global Learning Poverty. 2022 Update*. <https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/e52f55322528903b27f1b7e61238e416-0200022022/original/Learning-poverty-report-2022-06-21-final-v7-0-conferenceEdition.pdf>
19. Zheng, X., Zhang, D., Lau, E. N. S., Xu, Z., Zhang, Z., Mo, P. K. H., Yang, X., Mak, E. C. W., & Wong, S. Y. S. (2022). Primary School Students' Online Learning During Coronavirus Disease 2019: Factors Associated With Satisfaction, Perceived Effectiveness, and Preference. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.784826>